

NDAC/LO/034

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Small-scale experiments in Step 2/3 with elimination of astrometric parameters. II. Solutions including global parameters.

by S. Söderhjelm

1. Introduction

In part I of this report (NDAC/LO/032), we gave some preliminary results of simulations of the "new" Step 2/3 process. These simulations did only include the set zero-points and three (eliminated) astrometric parameters per star as unknowns. The present part II summarizes the results when a number of global parameters are also introduced. The final choice of globals can not yet be specified, but we give below some estimates of precision which should be rather generally applicable.

As before, the HP 9000 computer was used, but because of the increased computing times with the added globals and because of the increased load on the system from other users, some of the calculations have been performed in single precision. Comparisons with d.p. runs show very small differences which become significant only in some special cases.

2. The global parameters

Apart from increased computing and storage requirements, one may in principle include any number of globals in the normal equations. In the solution process any number of them can later be discarded, while the inclusion of unforeseen globals is impossible.

In the present experiments, we have introduced three groups of global parameters. The first group consists of the twelve Fourier coefficients ($\sin/\cos n\Psi$, $n = 1-6$) for a distortion related to the solar aspect angle $\Psi = \nu - \nu_{\odot}$. The second group consists of fifteen combinations of space-time metric coefficients as given by Cowling (1983). The third group is the two corrections to the classical and relativistic parts of the aberration.

The general equation

$$G_{ij}^{(\ell)} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial g_\ell} \quad (1)$$

shows the relation between the differential coefficients $G_{ij}^{(\ell)}$ and the corresponding global parameter g_ℓ .

3. Calculation of the differential coefficients

For the Fourier parameters g_1 - g_{12} we need only the star's abscissa and the corresponding solar abscissa. For simplicity (and with no real loss of accuracy), a single value for the sun's abscissa is used for the whole set. The star's abscissa is already needed for the A_{ij} -coefficients (cf. NDAC/LO/021), and we get $\cos/\sin \Psi$. The differential coefficients are then

$$\begin{aligned} G_{ij}^{(2k-1)} &\equiv \sin k\Psi \equiv \sin \Psi U_k(\cos \Psi) \\ G_{ij}^{(2k)} &\equiv \cos k\Psi \equiv T_k(\cos \Psi) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the T_k and U_k are standard Chebyshev polynomials.

The Cowling terms are more awkward. They too depend mostly on the angle Ψ , but also on angles η_p and ϕ_o . From Cowling's definitions, it appears that η_p is identical to $\pi - \nu$, where ν is the "position angle" in the revolving scanning. The angle ϕ_o is for the non-axisymmetric part of the metric, and it is taken here to be equal to the sun's geocentric longitude. Cowling (1983) has expanded his rigorous expressions in Fourier series in Ψ (for an assumed revolving angle $\xi = 43^\circ$), and we may abbreviate

$$\begin{aligned} S_k(\Psi) &\equiv \sum_{n=1}^6 s_{nk} \sin n\Psi & k=1-13 \\ C_k(\Psi) &\equiv \sum_{n=1}^6 c_{nk} \cos n\Psi & k=1-8 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with the coefficients s_{nk} , c_{nk} given in Tables la and lb.

Table 1a. Fourier sine coefficients s_{nk} defining the functions $S_k(\Psi)$.

k	s_{1k}	s_{2k}	s_{3k}	s_{4k}	s_{5k}	s_{6k}
1	0.394	0.155	0.061	0.024	0.010	0.004
2	0.304	0.171	0.080	0.035	0.015	0.006
3	0.671	0.345	0.162	0.073	0.032	0.014
4	0.057	0.488	0.288	0.151	0.075	0.035
5	-0.104	0.232	0.240	0.166	0.098	0.053
6	0.231	0.404	0.321	0.202	0.114	0.060
7	-0.070	0.653	0.328	0.152	0.068	0.030
8	-0.152	0.103	0.105	0.066	0.036	0.018
9	0.111	0.206	0.145	0.082	0.042	0.021
10	0.984	0.609	0.306	0.142	0.063	0.028
11	1.155	0.910	0.538	0.282	0.139	0.066
12	0.720	0.370	0.174	0.078	0.034	0.015
13	1.155	0.455	0.179	0.071	0.028	0.011

Table 1b. Fourier cosine coefficients c_{nk} defining the functions $C_k(\Psi)$.

k	c_{1k}	c_{2k}	c_{3k}	c_{4k}	c_{5k}	c_{6k}
1	0.083	0.488	0.288	0.151	0.075	0.035
2	0.152	0.645	0.564	0.369	0.212	0.113
3	-0.035	0.650	0.327	0.152	0.068	0.029
4	-0.041	0.309	0.250	0.149	0.079	0.039
5	1.280	0.702	0.337	0.153	0.067	0.029
6	1.155	0.910	0.538	0.282	0.139	0.066
7	0.842	0.411	0.188	0.083	0.036	0.015
8	0.845	0.333	0.131	0.052	0.020	0.008

In the notation of Cowling the metric parameters are

*brochure
numbers:*

$$13 \quad g_{13} = (A_{oo}^{(1)} + A_{ii}^{(1)})/r_o$$

$$g_{14} = (A_{oo}^{(1)} \mu_o + A_{ii}^{(1)} \mu_1)/r_o$$

$$14 \quad g_{15} = (A_{oo}^{(2)} + A_{ii}^{(2)})/r_o^2$$

$$15 \quad g_{16} = (B_{oo}^{(1)} + B_{ii}^{(1)})/r_o$$

$$g_{17} = (B_{oo}^{(2)} + B_{ii}^{(2)})/r_o^2$$

$$16 \quad g_{18} = B_{or}^{(1)}/r_o$$

$$17 \quad g_{19} = (A_{o\theta}^{(2)} - 2B_{or}^{(2)})/r_o^2$$

$$18 \quad g_{20} = A_{o\phi}^{(1)}/r_o$$

$$g_{21} = A_{o\phi}^{(2)}/r_o^2$$

$$19 \quad g_{22} = C/r_o$$

$$20 \quad g_{23} = D/r_o$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L} \quad g_{24} &= E/r_o \\
 g_{25} &= C_{ox} / r_o \\
 g_{26} &= C_{oy} / r_o \\
 g_{27} &= C_{oz} / r_o
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

with the following differential coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{ij}^{(13)} &= -S_1(\psi) \\
 G_{ij}^{(14)} &= -S_2(\psi) \\
 G_{ij}^{(15)} &= -S_3(\psi) \\
 G_{ij}^{(16)} &= -0.171 \sin \psi + S_4(\psi) \cos 2\eta_p - C_1(\psi) \sin 2\eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(17)} &= S_5(\psi) \cos^2 \eta_p - S_6(\psi) \sin^2 \eta_p - C_2(\psi) \cos \eta_p \sin \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(18)} &= 0.341 \sin \psi - S_7(\psi) \cos 2\eta_p + (C_3(\psi) - 0.052) \sin 2\eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(19)} &= S_8(\psi) \cos^2 \eta_p - S_9(\psi) \sin^2 \eta_p - (C_4(\psi) - 0.052) \sin \eta_p \cos \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(20)} &= -S_{10}(\psi) \cos \eta_p + (0.570 + C_5(\psi)) \sin \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(21)} &= -S_{11}(\psi) \cos \eta_p + C_6(\psi) \sin \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(22)} &= -(S_{12}(\psi) \cos \eta_p - C_7(\psi) \sin \eta_p) \sin \phi_o \\
 G_{ij}^{(23)} &= (S_{12}(\psi) \cos \eta_p - C_7(\psi) \sin \eta_p) \cos \phi_o \\
 G_{ij}^{(24)} &= S_{12}(\psi) \sin \eta_p + C_7(\psi) \cos \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(25)} &= S_{13}(\psi) (-0.682 \cos \phi_o + 0.731 \sin \phi_o \cos \eta_p) - \\
 &\quad - (C_8(\psi) - 0.394) \sin \phi_o \sin \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(26)} &= S_{13}(\psi) (-0.682 \sin \phi_o - 0.731 \cos \phi_o \cos \eta_p) + \\
 &\quad + (C_8(\psi) - 0.394) \cos \phi_o \sin \eta_p \\
 G_{ij}^{(27)} &= -0.731 S_{13}(\psi) \sin \eta_p - (C_8(\psi) - 0.394) \cos \eta_p
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

For the detailed interpretation of these parameters we refer to Cowling's work. Suffice it to say that r_o stands for the observer's distance from the sun, and that g_{13} is the only non-zero parameter if general relativity is correct. Because this general relativistic light-deflection is already used in the reductions, g_{13} will measure the correction to the relativistic value $4GM_{\odot}/r_o c^2 (= 8.14 \text{ mas})$. From previous tests of general relativity we should not expect any of these parameters to reach 0.1 mas.

In the HIPPARCOS reductions, the special relativistic formula for the stellar aberration is used (cf. note by Schutz). As a test it might be interesting to include two global parameters to measure the deviations of the first- and second-order (in v/c) contributions to the aberration. For the aberration in abscissa one may derive the equation

$$\Delta u = c^{-1} \sec^2 \rho \underline{v} \cdot (\underline{r} \times \underline{u}) [1 - 0.5 c^{-1} (\underline{v}' \underline{u})] \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{v}$ is the velocity vector, $\underline{r}$ the RGC pole unit vector and $\underline{u}$ the star position unit vector. For easy comparison with the other (absolute) global parameters we define

$$G_{ij}^{(28)} = \sec^2 \rho \underline{v} \cdot (\underline{r} \times \underline{u}) / v_1 \quad (7)$$

$$G_{ij}^{(29)} = -0.5 G_{ij}^{(28)} (\underline{v}' \underline{u}) / v_1$$

where $v_1 = (GM_{\odot}/a(1-e^2))^{1/2}$ is the earth's velocity as used for the standard aberration constant $\kappa_o = v_1/c$. With these definitions, the observed classical aberration constant will be $\kappa = \kappa_o + g_{28}$, and the coefficient -0.5 for the relativistic part will be $-0.5 (1 + g_{29} \kappa_o^{-2})$.

4. The numerical experiments

All the present experiments were made with the standard 0.9° FOV and with 5 scans per set. Generally, 2000 or 10000 stars were simulated (with NSET from 152 to 487), and the normal equations were formed as described in Part I of the report. Several different pseudo-solutions were then obtained from these n.e. by including different subsets of the global parameters, and the covariance matrix for the globals was derived in full. The correlations found in this way are further described in Sections 5 and 7. For the set zero-points, the simple arithmetic mean of the mean errors was taken as an

excellent approximation for the σ_0 defined in eq. (I,7). The magnitude of σ_0 is discussed in Section 6.

A few tests with (g_1-g_{12}) -solutions show that the eigenvalues found with $\text{NGLOB} = 0$ (see Part I) are virtually unchanged, the twelve new values being nearly equal to the diagonal elements in the "global part" of the n.e.. This is a natural result if the globals are uncorrelated (mutually and with respect to the set zero-points), and no further eigenvalue-calculations have been made.

5. Correlations between the global parameters

It is obvious already from the differential coefficients that the Cowling parameters $g_{13}-g_{15}$ are linearly dependent on the Fourier sine-terms. There are more subtle correlations, however, which will be described in this section.

The twelve Fourier parameters g_1-g_{12} are nearly orthogonal to each other, and numerically no correlations above some 0.25 are observed within the group. The coefficient $\sin(\nu - \nu_0)$ for g_1 is very nearly proportional to the parallax coefficients $A_{ij}^{(3)}$, however, and this correlation makes the mean error for g_1 very much larger than those for g_2-g_{12} . In effect, a g_1 -term due e.g. to thermal effects on the satellite can not be well separated from a parallax zero-point error.

The Cowling-parameters in the second group are not an ideal set. Especially, it turns out that $g_{25}-g_{27}$ are highly correlated with $g_{22}-g_{24}$ (correlation coefficients above 0.85). With the low probability of observing non-zero values for these non-axisymmetric terms, it seems quite useless to solve separately for all six. In the sequel, $g_{25}-g_{27}$ are not included. The remaining parameters show correlation coefficients above 0.5 for the following pairs: (14,15), (14,19), (15,19), (16,17) and (20,21). If we compare with the defining relations (4), it is seen that g_{15} , g_{17} , g_{19} and g_{21} are r_0^{-2} -terms which are again expected to be smaller than the corresponding r_0^{-1} -terms. (If the r_0^{-1} and r_0^{-2} -terms are of equal magnitude at $r_0 = 1$ a.u., the r_0^{-2} -term would be 100 times larger near the solar limb and would presumably have more easily observable consequences.) It is possible to include the isotropic r_0^{-2} -term g_{15} if g_{17} , g_{19} and g_{21} are left out, and the final "Cowling-group" consists then of the nine parameters g_{13} , g_{14} , g_{15} , g_{16} , g_{18} , g_{20} , g_{22} , g_{23} and g_{24} which show little mutual correlation.

As for the correlations between the Fourier-group and the Cowling-

group, this is a problem for g_{13} - g_{15} . Theoretically and in practice, it is impossible to include more than three Fourier sine-terms together with g_{13} - g_{15} , and with three sine-terms there are still correlations that increase the mean error of g_{13} . The other six Cowling-parameters are not correlated with the Fourier-group. See further Section 7.

The relativistic aberration-parameter g_{29} is also problematic. Surprisingly, g_{29} and g_3 are found to be almost perfectly correlated ($\rho \geq 0.995$), although their differential coefficients are not. Within each set, however, $G_{ij}^{(3)}$ and $G_{ij}^{(29)}$ are proportional, but with a proportionality factor that has different sign and amplitude for different sets. The correlation can be diminished to about $\rho = 0.98$ with an increased velocity-resolution (one v -value per scan instead of only one per set), but the fact remains that g_{29} is inseparable from a $\sin 2\Psi$ -distortion. With the Cowling-group, g_{29} is correlated with g_{13} , but much less extremely ($\rho \approx 0.7$).

6. The set zero-point errors

As a general statement, we may say that 10-20 global parameters (with no large internal correlations) can be included with very little effect on the set zero-points. In Part I of this report, we gave the ad hoc eq. (I,8) for the mean set zero-point error σ_o as a function of the number of sets included. A both simpler and more plausible relation is instead

$$\sigma_o^{zpt} = \sigma_v (N_{eff}^{zpt})^{-0.5} \quad (8)$$

where

$$N_{eff}^{zpt} = (\text{NOBS} - 3 \times \text{NSTAR}) / (\text{NSET} + \text{NGLOB}) - 1 \quad (9)$$

Here NOBS is the total number of (unit weight) abscissa observations and NSTAR the number of stars with more than 3 observations. The simple interpretation is of course that $3 \times \text{NSTAR}$ observations are "used up" for deriving the astrometric parameters, and thus $N_{eff}^{zpt} + 1$ observations remain for each of the $\text{NSET} + \text{NGLOB}$ remaining unknowns. Table 2 gives the observed and computed σ_o^{zpt} for a selection of solutions with $\text{NGLOB} = 12$ (Fourier-group). (N_* is the number of stars originally simulated, but with $\text{NSET} < 730$ some get less than 4 observations and are not used in the zero-point solution.)

The agreement is almost implausibly perfect, and the extrapolation to a "full" 730-set solution is quite certain.

Table 2. Mean set zero-point errors as function of NSET and N_* .

NSET	N_*	NSTAR	NOBS	$N_{\text{eff}}^{\text{zpt}}$	$(\sigma_o^{\text{zpt}}/\sigma_U)^{\text{obs}}$	$(\sigma_o^{\text{zpt}}/\sigma_U)^{\text{calc}}$
152	2000	630	3052	6.085	0.4048	0.4054
152	10000	3280	15860	35.71	0.1674	0.1673
182	2000	865	4400	8.305	0.3447	0.3470
209	2000	1091	5885	10.82	0.3028	0.3040
209	10000	5494	29511	57.95	0.1309	0.1314
230	10000	6217	34799	66.73	0.1229	0.1233
261	2000	1437	8472	14.24	0.2629	0.2650
261	10000	7087	41786	74.18	0.1159	0.1161
305	2000	1629	10586	16.98	0.2416	0.2427
305	10000	8111	52557	88.03	0.1064	0.1066
365	2000	1804	13239	19.76	0.2244	0.2250
487	2000	1999	18334	23.72	0.2047	0.2053

With NSET = 730 we have NSTAR = N_* and NOBS $\approx 13.68 N_*$ which gives (for NGLOB = 12) $N_{\text{eff}}^{\text{zpt}} = 0.01439 N_* - 1$. For stars of unequal weight, we may use eq. (I,9) to obtain w_{eff} , which is then substituted for N_* . Instead of eq. (I,10) we obtain now

$$\sigma_o^{\text{zpt}} = (0.01439 w_{\text{eff}} - 1)^{-0.5} \quad (10)$$

With the "typical" value $w_{\text{eff}} = 3774 \text{ mas}^{-2}$ we get $\sigma_o^{\text{zpt}} = 0.137 \text{ mas}$, in good agreement with the estimate in Part I.

7. Determinacy of the global parameters

From a lot of test solutions, it is apparent that the mean errors (from the inverse n.e. matrix) for the individual global parameters are fairly constant relative to each other, and that only the "mean level" varies significantly with NSET and N_* . Again, this mean level is given by the simple formula

$$\sigma_o^{\text{glob}} = \text{Const. } \sigma_U (N_{\text{eff}}^{\text{glob}})^{-0.5} \quad (11)$$

with

$$N_{\text{eff}}^{\text{glob}} = \text{NOBS} - 3 \times \text{NSTAR} - \text{NSET} - \text{NGLOB} = N_{\text{eff}}^{\text{zpt}} (\text{NSET} + \text{NGLOB}) \quad (12)$$

If we let the mean level be defined by the mean errors for g_2 - g_{12} , we get $\text{Const.} \approx 1.503$, and the excellent fit can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Mean global mean errors as function of NSET and N_* .

NSET	N_*	$N_{\text{eff}}^{\text{glob}}$	$(\sigma_o^{\text{zpt}}/\sigma_o)^{\text{obs}}$	$(\sigma_o^{\text{zpt}}/\sigma_o)^{\text{calc}}$
152	2000	998	0.0478	0.0476
152	10000	5856	0.0198	0.0196
182	2000	1611	0.0374	0.0374
209	2000	2391	0.0308	0.0307
209	10000	12808	0.0133	0.0133
230	10000	15906	0.0119	0.0119
261	2000	3888	0.0241	0.0241
261	10000	20252	0.0105	0.0106
305	2000	5382	0.0204	0.0205
305	10000	27907	0.00898	0.00900
365	2000	7450	0.0175	0.0174
487	2000	11838	(0.0142)	0.0138

Only for NSET = 487 does the observed mean error deviate significantly, but this is very probably due to numerical problems with the single precision solution. (A numerical noise of about $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ in the covariances is enough.) The "standard" global mean error for 730 sets will then be

$$\sigma_o^{\text{glob}} = 0.055 \sigma_o^{\text{zpt}} \quad (13)$$

With the above estimate for σ_o^{zpt} we find $\sigma_o^{\text{glob}} = 0.0075 \text{ mas}$.

It remains to specify the individual mean errors relative to σ_o^{glob} . Table 4 gives such ratios for eight illustrative selections of parameters. Columns A-C give the "minimal" errors for the uncorrelated globals in each group. Column D shows that the Cowling-parameters except g_{13} - g_{15} can be determined together with the full Fourier-group. Columns E-G show the successive increase of the mean error of g_{13} as more Fourier sine-terms are included (column H showing the near equivalence of g_3 and g_{29}). All these numbers are extrapolations to NSET = 730. The variation with NSET is slow, and we expect no extrapolation errors above some 5%.

Table 4. Mean errors relative to σ_0^{glob} for different parameter selections.

Var no.	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	91.	-	-	91.	91.	91.	91.	91.
2	1.24	-	-	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
3	0.84	-	-	0.85	-	1.89	2.01	-
4	1.02	-	-	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02
5	0.89	-	-	0.90	-	-	1.70	-
6	1.04	-	-	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05
7	0.93	-	-	0.96	-	-	-	-
8	1.05	-	-	1.06	1.06	1.06	1.06	1.06
9	0.95	-	-	0.95	-	-	-	-
10	1.10	-	-	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.10
11	0.99	-	-	1.02	-	-	-	-
12	0.96	-	-	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.96
13	-	2.23	-	-	2.23	3.29	6.04	3.34
14	-	1.52	-	-	1.52	1.54	1.54	1.53
15	-	0.96	-	-	0.96	0.97	0.99	0.96
16	-	0.92	-	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.93	0.92
18	-	1.30	-	1.32	1.30	1.30	1.33	1.30
20	-	1.03	-	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05
22	-	1.51	-	1.52	1.51	1.51	1.51	1.51
23	-	1.48	-	1.48	1.48	1.48	1.48	1.48
24	-	0.98	-	1.00	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99
28	-	-	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97
29	-	-	7.7	-	-	-	-	11.9

Several other parameter-combinations can be tried, but some important conclusions are apparent already from Table 4:

- 1) Except for g_1 , g_{13} and g_{29} , all global parameters have typical mean errors within 50% of σ_0^{glob} .
- 2) The $\sin \Psi$ Fourier parameter g_1 can not be determined to better than about $100 \sigma_0^{\text{glob}}$, and a parallax zero-point error this large is undetectable.
- 3) The six Cowling-parameters g_{16} , g_{18} , g_{20} , g_{22} , g_{23} and g_{24} can be well determined together with the Fourier distortion. They correspond to non-isotropic metric coefficients which are thus detectable to high accuracy.
- 4) If the Fourier-parameters as determined e.g. from a "D"-solution are all large, it will be impossible to determine an accurate value for the GR light-deflection (g_{13}). Only if at least g_{11} , g_9 and g_7 can be set to zero we may estimate g_{13} with some accuracy. Interestingly, g_{14} and g_{15} have small mean errors even in this ("G") case.
- 5) The relativistic aberration parameter is so strongly correlated with the $\sin 2\Psi$ Fourier-term that it will in practice be indeterminable.

The above 730-set accuracy estimates refer to a 1-year period. For the full 2.5-year mission we may expect a further reduction of σ_0^{glob} to about 0.005 mas.

8. Conclusions

In this and the previous report we have shown by numerical simulations that the new Step 2/3 solution method described by Lindegren (NDAC/LO/021-22) is practically feasible and that it gives much more accurate results than the old PRS-method. In the present report, we have investigated in particular the determinacy of global distortion parameters. This is straightforward in principle, but in practice it will be difficult to separate "real" space-time metric effects from "apparent" satellite distortions.

Using a representative set of space-time metric coefficients, we have shown that the non-isotropic ones may be determined with a mean error not much larger than 0.01 mas. For the isotropic ones, in particular the standard general relativity light deflection, the correlation with Fourier sine distortion terms will make their determination difficult. Only if the Fourier parameters for 4Ψ , 5Ψ and 6Ψ turn out to be very small will the light-deflection be measurable with an interesting accuracy (less than 1% of the GR value).

Independently of the cause of the observed distortions, their influence on the astrometric parameters may be corrected with negligible error. The important exception is that a parallax zero-point error of magnitude less than about 1 mas can not be separated from a $\sin \Psi$ distortion in the satellite.